

On the ‘rigidity’ of the force field of a moving source

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Abstract

In the present paper, we propose a heuristic and intuitive approach to visualize how force fields ‘move’ when their source moves at a constant velocity v or accelerates with acceleration a relative to a stationary observer. Our approach is based on the application of the principle of relativity and the principle of equivalence and holds regardless of the nature of the force field. The results presented here have been derived in the non-relativistic approximation ($v \ll c$ and $a\Delta t \ll c$, Δt being the interval of time within which we observe the field). We shall show that in both cases of uniform and accelerated motion of the source, the field moves rigidly with the source. Namely, for every observer, however distant from the source, the field is always directed away from (or points towards) the *present, instantaneous* position of the source. We also show that these results are in agreement with what we know from experimental evidence and full-fledged physical theories (of electromagnetism and gravitation) beyond the non-relativistic approximation. The proposed approach may be considered as a tool to facilitate students in graduate and undergraduate courses to familiarize themselves with (and self convince of) such a counter-intuitive feature of the force fields.

Keywords: force field, electromagnetism, gravity, special and general relativity, principle of relativity, principle of equivalence, simultaneity

1 Introduction

The physical problem of what happens to a force field when its source moves relative to an assumed stationary observer is treated from different perspectives in literature. For instance, depending on the nature of the force field under study (electric, magnetic, gravitational), not only the field generated by the moving source changes with respect to that generated when the source is stationary with the observer, but other induced fields may appear (e.g. magnetic, electric and gravitomagnetic fields, respectively).

In the present paper, we shall consider only a specific aspect of this vast area of study. We focus on how the field lines generated by the source ‘move’ with the source, or on what we may call *rigidity* of the field with respect to the source when the source is seen by a (relatively) stationary observer. Bear in mind that *rigidity* here must be intended in a figurative sense and does not have the same meaning referred to material bodies as in classical (non-relativistic) mechanics. We shall do this by applying the principle of relativity and the principle of equivalence and in the approximation of non-relativistic motion of the source (and the observer). In the case of a constant velocity of the source relative to the observer, we consider velocities $v \ll c$, where c is the speed of light in the vacuum. In the case of accelerated motion (of the source or the observer), we consider acceleration a such that $a\Delta t \ll c$, where Δt is the interval of time within which we observe the field. Moreover, we do not deliberately specify the type of force field (electric, magnetic, gravitational) or the type of source (charges, masses) since our approach to the problem turns out to be general in that regard.

What this paper is not about. The present analysis does not take into account the fields induced by the motion of the source. We focus only on how the field generated when the source is at rest (relative to an observer) behaves when the source moves. For instance, we all know that when a charge moves, it generates also a magnetic field (and even an electromagnetic field if it accelerates), but we stick to what happens to the static electric field (how this field moves) when the source moves relative to a stationary observer. We also do not derive nor deal with the change of the overall geometry of the field due to the relative motion: within the above-mentioned non-relativistic approximation, the relativistic change in shape (‘deformation’) of the field as a whole is negligible.

The whole matter is not new, at least for electromagnetism. At the end of 1800, Liénard and Wiechert introduced what is now known as the

Liénard-Wiechert potentials. These potentials derive directly from Maxwell's equations and describe the complete, relativistically correct, time-varying electromagnetic field for a point charge in arbitrary motion (see [2]). In more recent years, Purcell and Feynman derived the electric field of a point charge moving with a constant velocity by applying the Lorentz transformations of fields and space-time coordinates [1, 2].

In the present paper, we show how the rigidity of the field relative to the source can be easily obtained (within the above-mentioned non-relativistic approximation) with the only use of the principle of relativity and the principle of equivalence. We also show how our approach allows us to derive this regardless of the nature of the force field and the type of source (mass, charge, etc.).

2 Field of a point source moving with a constant velocity $v \ll c$

Let us start by considering the electric field of a point charge. By applying the Lorentz transformations of fields and space-time coordinates, Purcell [1] and Feynman [2] derived the electric field of a point charge moving with a constant velocity. The result is obviously in agreement with what can be derived from the Liénard-Wiechert potentials [2], but Purcell and Feynman's derivations are probably easier since special relativity is now more widely known among undergraduate and graduate physics students.

Consider a point charge q that moves with uniform velocity v along the x -axis of the inertial reference frame S of the observer, and let q be momentarily at the origin. If r denotes the distance from the charge q to the point (x, z) where the field is measured, then $r = (x^2 + z^2)^{1/2}$. For the sake of simplicity, we consider a point on the xz plane. Owing to the cylindrical symmetry of the problem, this does not make any difference. Let θ denote the angle between this radius vector and the velocity of the charge q (x -axis), see Fig. 1. Then since $z = r \sin \theta$, the magnitude of the field can be written as

$$E = \frac{q}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r^2} \frac{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}{\left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \sin^2 \theta\right)^{3/2}}, \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity. As already noticed, there is nothing

Figure 1: The point charge q moves with uniform velocity v along the x -axis of the inertial reference frame S of the observer, and it is momentarily at the origin. If the velocity v is such that v^2/c^2 is not negligible, the electric field gets stronger at right angles to the motion than in the direction of the motion (see eq. (1)).

special about the origin of coordinates, nor about the xz plane as compared with any other plane through the x -axis. Then, the electric field of a charge that has been in uniform motion is at a given instant of time directed radially towards, or away from, the *instantaneous* position of the charge, while its magnitude is given by eq. (1).

There are at least two interesting aspects of this result. The first is that the electric field of a point charge is no more spherical-symmetric: its magnitude is higher on the plane perpendicular to the velocity direction and smaller along that direction (Fig. 1). This consequence cannot be obtained without the application of special relativity or the Liénard-Wiechert potentials. Unfortunately, the approach that we shall present in this paper does not provide us with information on the ‘shape’ of the field and cannot help in this regard.

The second interesting aspect is that the field is from any point of observation and at any instant of time directed radially towards, or away from, the *actual, instantaneous* position of the charge. This appears to be quite bizarre.

Quoting Purcell's words [1] almost verbatim, it means that if q passed the origin of the system S at precisely 12:00 noon, S time, an observer stationed anywhere in the system S would report that the electric field in his vicinity was pointing, at 12:00 noon, exactly radially from the origin. This sounds like instantaneous transmission of information since the information would take some time to cover the distance separating the source q and the observer. Purcell assures that it is not an instantaneous transmission of information and this particular feature of the field cannot be used to violate causality [1].

As a matter of fact, it is as if the electric field of q , however deformed, always moves *rigidly* with the charge (even at an infinite distance from it) when the charge moves with a constant velocity.

In fact, this peculiar aspect can be easily derived by applying the sole principle of relativity, at least in the non-relativistic approximation $v \ll c$. The approximation does not make the explicative power of the approach we are going to present any weaker since the apparent counter-intuitiveness of the *rigidity* of the field does not depend upon the relative velocity. Even for low relative velocities, if the source is at a great distance from the observer, the observer will see the local force field pointing radially towards, or away from, the *actual* position of the source, but he will see the image of the source in a retarded position due to the time taken by light to travel that great distance.

The present method can be introduced as a heuristic and simple approach to acquaint students with such a counter-intuitive feature of the force fields. Moreover, as we shall see, the following approach does not require the source to be an electric charge. The argument holds for every force field source.

Consider a force field source stationary in the inertial system S . In this system, we may represent the field lines like in Fig. 2-a. Imagine further an observer S' that moves with velocity $v \ll c$. During his motion, this observer sees at each location the field lines as rigidly attached to the source and always pointing radially towards, or away from, the instantaneous position of the source: the source is stationary in S , and its field lines are fixed relative to the source. It is like what a driver moving at a constant velocity sees when he moves across a forest: the trees (field lines) move rigidly with the 'center' of the forest (field source). We cautiously assume the non-relativistic approximation ($v \ll c$) since, in that case, the whole geometry of what the observer sees is practically not affected by relativistic deformation.

Now, according to the principle of relativity, there is no point in saying that the source is stationary and the observer is moving. It may well be

Figure 2: a) Observer S' moving at a constant velocity v passing by a stationary force field source Q ; b) Force field source Q moving at a constant velocity v passing by a stationary observer S' .

the other way around. Therefore, if we imagine the observer as stationary and the source as moving (Fig. 2-b), then what we have previously said does not change and the stationary observer will see the moving source and the field lines as a single rigid block, no matter how distant the observer is from the source. To him, the field will always point radially outward along a line drawn from the *instantaneous* position of the source. We now know that the field will have different ‘shapes’ at different velocities v , but the fact that it is rigidly attached to the moving source is a simple consequence of the principle of relativity.

A quick mention of the connection between the field always pointing towards the source’s instantaneous position and the principle of relativity is already given in [3].

2.1 A special case: the field of a shrinking dipole

Consider two equal metallic spheres separated by a great distance and forced to move towards each other at a constant velocity v relative to a distant, stationary observer. The spheres are charged respectively with charge q and

$-q$ (total charge equal to zero)¹ and generate two distinct electric fields. The system described here represents a sort of shrinking dipole. According to the previous results, the observer measures at his location a total field that is the vector sum of the two fields pointing radially towards, or away from, the *actual, instantaneous* positions of the moving charges, no matter how distant these charges are from the observer.

Now, consider what happens when the two charges collide and stick together (inelastic collision). The spheres suddenly stop (conservation of linear momentum), and the total charge and field become equal to zero. This is what happens in the proximity of the two spheres. What does happen *at the same instant of time* close to the distant observer? In every phase of the collision process, the field measured by the observer is always the vector sum of the two fields pointing radially towards, or away from, the *actual, instantaneous* positions of the moving charges. Just before the collision, the sum of the two fields perceived by the observer is obviously equal to zero since in the proximity of the observer we have two equal fields pointing in opposite directions. This means that the observer will *instantaneously* perceive the zeroing of the total charge no matter how distant is this observer from the charges. This is not magic. This is a direct consequence of the accepted physics. It has been shown elsewhere [4] that this property has some surprising consequences for the relativity of simultaneity.

3 Field of a point source in the case of accelerated motion with $a\Delta t \ll c$

We now apply the same heuristic and qualitative approach as in Section 2 to the case of an accelerating field source, or an accelerating observer, always in the non-relativistic approximation $a\Delta t \ll c$, where Δt is the interval of time within which we study the field. By applying this time the principle of equivalence, we shall show how it is possible to obtain some interesting features of the force fields when the source accelerates.

Our procedure bears similarities with the thought experiment described by Einstein in his 1918 paper [5]: there, he uses the general theory of rela-

¹If two oppositely charged spheres were left to move freely, they would accelerate towards each other, and the result reached in this Section cannot be applied. This is the reason why in the text we say that they are forced to move at a constant velocity. In Section 3, we will see that in fact this condition can be weakened.

Figure 3: a) Observer S' accelerates with acceleration a towards the source Q , stationary in the inertial frame S ; b) The source Q free-falls with acceleration $-a$ while observer S' is stationary in a global homogeneous gravitational field $-a$.

tivity to resolve the twin paradox and makes use of the acceleration and its equivalence to a homogeneous gravitational field.

Let us start with a force field source Q stationary in the inertial reference frame S and an observer in S' moving with an acceleration a such that $a\Delta t \ll c$, as represented in Fig. 3-a.

As in the case described in Section 2, during his motion the observer will see at each location the field lines as rigidly attached to the source and always pointing towards, or away from, the instantaneous position of the source: the source is stationary in S , and its field lines are fixed relative to the source. For the sake of argument, the observer is like a driver slowly accelerating in his car. He will see the road network leading to the center of the city as moving rigidly with the city and always pointing to the instantaneous position of the center of the city.

Now, according to the principle of equivalence, we can equivalently consider the observer as stationary in a global homogeneous gravitational field $-a$ and the force field source Q as free-falling (accelerating) in this gravity field (Fig. 3-b). Notice that it is always possible to get close to a homogeneous gravitational field. Consider an imaginary spherical planet of mass M and radius R such that its surface gravity $g = \frac{GM}{R^2}$ (G is the gravitational

constant) has exactly the numerical value we want. The variation of the gravity Δg with the distance d from the surface of the planet is then

$$\Delta g \simeq -2 \frac{GM}{R^3} d = -2g \frac{d}{R}, \quad (2)$$

and thus, it is always possible to choose d and R such that $\Delta g \simeq 0$, namely the gravitational field is practically homogeneous within the distance d from the surface.

Now, the observer stationary in the homogeneous gravitational field will see the source as accelerating (free-falling), and he will see, as in the previous equivalent perspective, its field lines as moving rigidly with it, no matter how distant the observer is from the source. To him, the field will always point radially outward along a line drawn from the *instantaneous* position of the source.

Let us consider this time the case of a force field source stationary in a homogeneous gravitational field $-a$ and the observer initially at zero relative velocity and free-falling (accelerating) towards the planet with acceleration $-a$. Notice that, in this case, the reference frame S of the observer is still an inertial frame (Fig. 4-a).

Since the field source and the field lines are stationary, during his free-fall motion the observer will see at each location the field lines as rigidly attached to the source and always pointing towards, or away from, the instantaneous position of the source: the source is stationary in S , and its field lines are fixed relative to the source. The fact that the source and the field lines are stationary in a gravitational field does not affect the conclusion. As a matter of fact, in the previous analogy with the road network and the city center, all that setting is also in a gravitational field, that of the Earth.

Why is the equivalence principle so important in this scenario? The scenario depicted in Fig. 4-a is equivalent to that of an observer stationary in the inertial frame S' and a force field source starting to move towards the observer with acceleration a , always in the approximation $a\Delta t \ll c$ (Fig. 4-b).

All this means that even when a force field source accelerates towards a stationary observer, this observer sees the field lines as rigidly attached to the source and pointing radially outward along a line drawn from the instantaneous position of the source.

Figure 4: a) The source Q and its field are stationary in a homogeneous gravitational field $-a$ while observer S' , starting at zero relative velocity, free-falls towards the planet with acceleration $-a$ (S' reference frame is inertial); b) The source Q accelerates with acceleration a towards the observer, stationary in the inertial frame S' .

4 Discussion and Conclusion

We guess that two questions naturally arise: i) why did we make the non-relativistic approximation? And ii) do our results hold also beyond the non-relativistic approximation?

We use the non-relativistic approximation because it makes some steps of our derivation easier to understand, more intuitive, and closer to everyday experience. For instance, when in Section 2 (Fig. 2-a, Fig. 3-a, and Fig. 4-a) we assert that during his motion the observer sees at each location the field lines as rigidly attached to the source and always pointing towards, or away from, the instantaneous position of the source, we rely on an easily imaginable thought experiment with reference to direct experience attainable by the reader. Imagine a non-conductive thick fluid (e.g. oil) around a stationary electric charge filled with a fine suspended non-conductive powder. The electric field could then be visualized thanks to the orientation of the polarized powder. If an observer is in motion relative to the charge (with a very small constant velocity or acceleration), then he actually sees the polarized

Figure 5: Eddington's example.

powder and the field as *rigidly* attached to the source. All this becomes not so obvious if $v \simeq c$ or $a\Delta t \simeq c$. No one directly perceives how the observed geometry changes when relativity comes heavily into play.

Let us now discuss question ii). For constant relative velocity v , equation (1) and the theory behind it (special relativity or the Liénard-Wiechert potentials) tell us that the rigid movement of the force field with the source holds also beyond the non-relativistic approximation. The field gets increasingly deformed (change of the whole geometrical shape) for higher values of v , but its 'rigidity' is still there.

Regarding the validity of the results obtained in Section 3, we have experimental and theoretical corroborations, at least for the gravitational force field.

If we consider an isolated gravitationally-bound system of bodies, like a planetary system, a galaxy, or close and fast rotating binary stars, each mass is the source of a force field, and each mass accelerates. This notwithstanding, the gravitational force acting upon each of these masses is the sum of all the forces exerted by the other masses pointing towards their *instantaneous* positions. This is true even if the distance between each mass is such that the time needed by light to cover that distance makes them clearly appear in a different (retarded) position.

This is implicitly assumed in every orbit computation. If one would introduce a delay in gravitational interactions, then the effect on computed orbits would be usually disastrous because the conservation of angular momentum

is destroyed [6].

With reference to the Sun and Jupiter, Sir Arthur Eddington expressed this feature like this (see Fig. 5): “If the Sun attracts Jupiter towards its present position S , and Jupiter attracts the Sun towards its present position J , the two forces are in the same line and balance. But if the Sun attracts Jupiter towards its previous position S' , and Jupiter attracts the Sun towards its previous position J' , when the force of attraction started out to cross the gulf, then the two forces give a couple. This couple will tend to increase the angular momentum of the system, and, acting cumulatively, will soon cause an appreciable change of period, disagreeing with observations [...]” [7].

As previously stated, the approach described in Section 2 represents a heuristic and intuitive way to realize that the field of a source moving at a constant velocity moves rigidly with the source and, although it was developed in the non-relativistic approximation, is in agreement with what the full theory (special relativity or the Liénard-Wiechert potentials) prescribes for every constant velocity. Likewise, the approach described in Section 3, which represents in the non-relativistic approximation a heuristic and intuitive way to realize that also the field of an accelerating source moves rigidly with the source, agrees with experimental evidence in orbit computation and with the theory of general relativity.

According to general relativity [3], the gravitational force exerted by an accelerating source (mass) is directed towards its instantaneous position and the gravitational aberration (namely, the direction of the force towards the retarded position rather than the instantaneous position) is almost exactly canceled by velocity-dependent interactions. While at first, this cancellation seems to be ‘miraculous’, it can be explained also from first principles: conservation of energy and angular momentum [3].

The conclusions reached in Section 3 must hold also for fields generated by electric charges or magnetic sources. The logic behind our approach is independent of the nature of the force field: it does not matter if the source is a mass or a charge since the definition and the basic properties of the force field are the same. Moreover, with reference to the previously given quotation, Eddington added: “Indeed it is found that if S and J are two electrical charges, S will be attracted very approximately towards J (not J') in spite of the electric influence being propagated with the velocity of light” [7]. Although the motion of both S and J in this example is circular and thus accelerated (Fig. 5), Eddington considered this fact as a natural consequence the Liénard-Wiechert potentials, see Note 6 in [7]. However, as

we have seen in Section 2, Liénard-Wiechert potentials have been used to derive the field of a charge moving at a constant velocity, and only in that case they show that the field moves rigidly with the source. In any case, the same first principle considerations on the conservation of energy and angular momentum made for the gravitational force do hold also for electric and magnetic fields.

In conclusion, in the present paper we propose a heuristic and intuitive approach to visualize how the force fields ‘move’ when the source moves at a constant velocity v or accelerates with acceleration a . Our approach is based on the application of the principle of relativity and the principle of equivalence and holds in the non-relativistic approximation ($v \ll c$ and $a\Delta t \ll c$, Δt being the interval of time within which we observe the field) regardless of the nature of the force field. It has been shown that in both cases of uniform and accelerated motion of the source, the field moves rigidly with the source. We have also shown that these results are in agreement with what we know from experimental evidence and full-fledged physical theories (of electromagnetism and gravitation). The proposed approach may be considered as a tool to facilitate students in graduate and undergraduate courses to familiarize themselves with (and self convince of) such a counter-intuitive feature of the force fields.

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References

- [1] Purcell E M and Morin D J 2013 *Electricity and Magnetism* 3rd edn (Newton, MA: Harvard University) pp 259-264.
- [2] Feynman R P, Leighton R B and Sands M 1964 *The Feynman Lectures on Physics* vol. 2 (Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley) Chapters 21 and 26.2
- [3] Carlip S 2000 Aberration and the speed of gravity *Phys. Lett. A* **267** 81–7

- [4] D’Abramo G 2020 Faster-than-light: signaling with moving electric fields, submitted
- [5] Einstein A 1918 Dialog über Einwände gegen die Relativitätstheorie *Die Naturwissenschaften* **6** 697–702
- [6] Van Flandern T 1998 The speed of gravity – What the experiments say *Phys. Lett. A* **250** 1–11
- [7] Eddington, A M 1920 *Space, time and gravitation* (Cambridge: Cambridge Univ. Press, 1987) p 94

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